

Women Entrepreneurs - A Study With Special Reference to Beauty Parlours in Virudhunagar District

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Abstract

Women have a great role to play in the development and nurturing of society. Women entrepreneurs have been making a significant impact in all segments of the economy in India. Modern women have a strong desire and urge for enhancing their beauty. Hence, the present study specially deals with beauty parlour women entrepreneurs. So the present study is an attempt to identify the factors which influence the women to start the beauty parlours and the effect of variables like age, marital status, education and to suggest measures to improve their overall efficiency.

Keywords: Women entrepreneur, beauty parlour.

Introduction

In earlier days women were confined to the four walls of house and led a protected life. In the present modern society they have come out of the four walls and take part in all forms of activities competing successfully with men. Today there is a greater awakening among women. To look smart and decent is a right of every woman. Beautiful women are an eye-catcher. It shows her independence, her understanding of her surroundings and it gives a message about her like a visiting card. To fulfill their needs of curiosity there is an increase in the number of 'Beauty Parlours' in our country. Entrepreneurship paves the way for finding solution for the problems of unemployment. Developments of beauty attract many enthusiastic young people to undertake the beauty parlours.

The modern Indian women, especially those in the cities are exposed to education and training. The educated women have certain ambitions, acquired knowledge and experience and basic skill, competency and self assurance. In spite of the above, the number of women entrepreneurs who have set up business. They face many challenges in To-day's business world. In this context, it is felt necessary to study the role of women entrepreneurs. Hence, this study is aimed at identifying the factors which influence women entrepreneurs.

Statement of The Problem

Today's business world women entrepreneurs face many challenges. The economic stresses and strains the modern society brought forth in its wake have compelled many women to come out to augment their family outcome. In this context, it is necessary to study the role of women entrepreneurs. Hence, this study is aimed at identifying the factors which influence women entrepreneurs.

Literature on Previous Studies

Anitha, H.S and Laxmisha, A.S (1999), in their study found that inefficient arrangements for marketing are produced by women entrepreneurs.

Joshi, J. and MadhuriDeshpande (2002), in their study revealed that illiteracy has been the major barrier for women entrepreneurship development and also lack of information and skill for choosing an activity is another major hurdle for development of women entrepreneurship.

Meenambigai, J. (2004), in her study observed that to strengthen women's empowerment, female literacy has to be promoted and should be supported by economic independence.

Ramachandran, S. (2004) in his study revealed that women entrepreneur is self-aware, confident and comfortable with herself.

Objectives of the Study

The present study is based on the following objectives:

1. To analyse the socio-economic background of women entrepreneurs.
2. To identify the factors which influence the women to start the beauty parlours.
3. To examine the problems of beauty parlour entrepreneurs in promoting their units and to offer suggestions.

Hypotheses

In view of the earlier stated objectives the investigator of the present study has formulated the following hypotheses.

1. There is no significant difference between the experience and inexperience in problems faced by the women entrepreneurs.
2. There is no significant difference between the under graduate and graduate in problems faced by the women entrepreneurs.

Research Methodology

For the present study, the Virudhunagar district was selected. Because Virudhunagar District is a main business center. Recently there is space in women entrepreneurs in Virudhunagar Districts. In order to conduct the study, the well-structured interview schedule was prepared and administered to the beauty parlour women entrepreneurs who had already setup their units. In order to achieve the objectives of the present study a sample of 40 beauty parlour women entrepreneur units in Virudhunagar District were selected by using simple random sampling method.

Tools of Analysis

For the analysis of the data and testing the hypotheses were used by appropriate statistical tools such as Percentages, Garrett Ranking and t-test.

Results and Interpretation

The statistically analyses data was presented in the following Tables.

Table 1 Socio-Economic Profile

Sample	Sub-sample	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Age	Below 30years	10	25
	Above 30 years	30	75
Education qualification	Under graduate	27	68
	Graduate	13	32
Type of family	Joint	8	20
	Nuclear	32	80
Marital status	Married	38	95
	Unmarried	2	5
Marital status	Rural	12	30
	Urban	28	70

From Table 1, it was showed that, the socio-economic profile of the entire sample respondents.

Table 2 Factors Influencing Women Entrepreneurs

Factors	List of factors	Total Score	Rating Percent	Rank
Ambitions	To secure self-employment	2580	32	I
	To improve status	1848	23	III
	To earn money	2516	31	II
	To continue family business	1136	14	IV
Reasoning	Heavy demand	2461	30	I
	Higher profit margin	1917	24	II
	Easy to start and maintain	2225	28	II
	No competition	1477	18	IV

From Table 2, it was showed that the factors influencing women entrepreneurs such as ambitions and reasoning factors were rated by Garrett ranking.

Table 3 Problems Faced by the Women Entrepreneurs

Problem Factors	t- test	Table value @ 5% level	Level of signification
Experience	2.35	1.96	Significant
Educational level	6.08	1.96	Significant

From the Table 3 reveals that the problems of experience and inexperienced women entrepreneurs and the problems of under graduation and graduation are tested by using t – test. Since the calculated value of t (2.35 and 6.08) is more than the table value 1.96. Hence there is a significant relationship between the variables.

Major Findings of the Study

- Most of the respondents (75 percent) are in the age group of above 30 years.
- Majority of the respondents (68 percent) are belongs to under graduation.
- Most of the respondents (80 percent) are belongs to nuclear family.
- Most of the respondents (95 percent) are married.
- Majority of the respondents (70 percent) are belongs to urban areas.

- Most of the respondents (32 percent) of ambition factors, 'Self Employment' secured rank first.
- Majority of the respondents (30 percent) of reasoning factors, 'Heavy Demand' secured rank second.
- By using t-test it is found that there is significant difference between experienced and inexperienced about problems of beauty parlour women entrepreneurs.
- There is a significant difference between the respondents having under graduate and graduate groups.

Suggestions

- The majority of the beauty parlours in the Virudhunagar District came into existence only after 2000. Women entrepreneurs have been facing the problems of finance. The government provides financial support to entrepreneurs and give subsidy to women entrepreneurs. But most of the respondents are not interested to get a loan from government and banks because they will have to comply with several formalities. So the government has to liberalize the formalities.
- Improper location affects the development of entrepreneurship. So entrepreneurs must give more importance for selecting the location.
- Beauty parlour women entrepreneurs must promote their marketing strategies, they undergo training course and update themselves.
- Banks and financial institutions must educate the women entrepreneurs for getting loan procedures and formalities.
- Lack of education is another major hurdle for development of women entrepreneurship. So the government must take effective steps to educate the women entrepreneurs through conferences, seminars, training programs, awareness campus and other related activities.

Conclusion

In the modern era women play very important role in economic development. To achieve the goal of economic development in a country, it is necessary to increase the women entrepreneurship both qualitatively and quantitatively.

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